

A Review on Building Services Modeling for Hospital Building Using Revit Bim

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Abstract— Building Information Modelling (BIM) technology is rapidly gaining traction in facility management and operations. This software aids in the efficient management and exchange of building data, offering valuable benefits throughout construction stages, from planning to maintenance. This study delves into the factors affecting the operational efficiency of a BIM model and its outstanding benefits during the digital design phase. Concentration is placed on the merits of BIM during the operational phase, primarily using Autodesk Revit software. The research includes an evaluation of engineering systems, particularly digital modelling of HVAC, Fire Fighting, water supply, and electrical systems. The study reviewed significant grants to digital model designs, examining BIM models across various infrastructure projects. A unique appearance of this research is the elaboration of a digital BIM model using Autodesk Revit 2020.

Keywords— Building Information Modelling (BIM) Revit; Navis-work for clash deduction; digitalization, BIM, software, Autodesk Revit, digital model

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, numerous operations and processes are facilitated by computer technologies, which encompass a range of information transformations in various forms, such as textual, graphical, and auditory, into a digital format known as digitization. Digitization combines advanced technologies and systems from architecture, engineering, and construction, transitioning from traditional design methods to contemporary approaches using Building Information Modelling (BIM) (Tan et al., 2021).

Although initial attempts to apply computer technologies

in a building projects date come back to the early 1980s and 1990s, the most important enrollment of such technologies in the early 2000s when computer technologies entered the era of modernization and optimization in building design. The concept of the "Building Information Model" appeared in the early 1990s but gained prominence in the early 2000s when software provider Autodesk published an article titled "Building Information Modelling" (BIM), followed by other software companies joining the field (Panteli & Fokaidis, 2020).

The digitization of building information modelling (BIM) involves complex undertaking for developing an intelligent model that integrates professionals from architecture, engineering, and construction to insure efficiency in building design, construction, and operational phases. The primary advantage of BIM technology lies in developing and using computer-generated n-dimensional (n-D) models to simulate the facility's planning, design, construction, and operation. It enables architects, engineers, and builders to envision what will be constructed within the modeled atmosphere while also identifying probable design, construction, or operational issues (Ibem et al., 2018).

Figure 1: MEP 3D Model

However, BIM implementation has been slow particularly among small-to-medium enterprises. Many solutions to bad performance have either focused upon technical issues (such as: software compatibility, cost of software and employee training) or non-technical issues (such as: legal ambiguity, cultural change, disarranging in workflow, project delivery and contracts). However, resolving these issues requires a deeper and well-informed of critical success factors (CSFs) used for measuring the successful implementation of BIM.

Building information modelling (BIM) has revolutionized building and infrastructure development within the

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construction industry over the last decade. A plethora of studies expound the virtues of BIM implementation throughout a development's whole life cycle. However, BIM implementation has been slow particularly among small-to-medium enterprises. Many solutions to bad performance have either focused upon technical issues (such as: software compatibility, cost of software and employee training) or non-technical issues. However, resolving these issues requires a deeper and well-informed of critical success factors (CSFs) used for measuring the successful implementation of BIM.

Objectives

- To know what is building information modelling.
- Understand the user interface, parametric objects, families and templates.
- Create and modify levels and grids.
- Learn how to use modelling tool and constraints.
- Learn the benefits of the software.
- How to use it adequate in the industry to become more employable.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Zhen-Zhong Hu et al (2018) proposed to apply the BIM technology to build up a comprehensive as-built building model containing MEP related information for delivery. An algorithm of generating the GIS map based on the BIM information. Improving the efficiency of the MEP system is crucial for the success of a building project and is a primary goal of Operational and maintenance management. Furthermore, the current study investigates at crossplatform O&M intelligent management software, which is useful in raising O&M management efficiency and improving emergency response performance.

Rakesh Reddy et al (2019) explained Design and modelling of G+ 5 commercial building by Autodesk Revit architecture, which renders complete perspective of the construction. The building model is integrated with Revit architecture, Revit MEP, and Revit structures utilizing BIM technology. Every project completed in Revit will have 2d, 3d, section views, elevations with details and schedules, and quantities. The three-dimensional realistic image gives a detailed picture of the family and the components installed within the building model. This project provides comprehensive building modelling and precise families ranging from furniture to lighting fixtures, as well as the ability to import existing models from other softwares such as Auto CAD, etc.

A S Hadi et al (2020) carried out the Integrity of Revit with structural analysis software and this study analyses how engineers can benefit from using Building Information Modeling (BIM). The compatibility of Revit with structural analysis tools such as Robot Structural Analysis and E-tabs is being investigated. It offers the reinforcement area necessary

for all frames in the structure. The amount of reinforcement estimated using Revit for columns, walls, and floors according to what was designed at RSA and E-tabs was compared to the building's actual reinforcements. BIM allows structural engineers to evaluate numerous structural possibilities and optimise the optimum scenario to achieve the most cost-effective design with the least errors. In addition, BIM models preserve all analysis, design, and documentation information in one place.

Sachin A et al (2020) outlined a Case Study on Building Information Modelling for Residential Buildings. This project is studying BIM application on an existing building, which has G+1 floor and a total built up area. BIM enables more intelligent resource use and process optimization, resulting in increased productivity and probability. The purpose is to utilise BIM to visualise, 3D coordinates, plan, schedule, estimate, and record a residential building. The following are the uses of Building information modelling that serve mostly by the function that they fulfil on the project, as well as additional attributes for each BIM such as Virtual construction, Design and engineering, Construction management, Operations and maintenance.

CONCLUSION

The Preceding research emphasises the use of BIM in Revit software. The BIM is an unique and promising strategy being used by owners, architects, engineers, and builders in India over time. BIM is used in the study for visualisation, 3D coordinates, planning, scheduling, estimate, and record-keeping. A good image of the family and the essential included in the construction model is provided by a three-dimensional realistic view. Autodesk Revit software will be used for architectural design, including mechanical, electrical, and plumbing services (MEP).

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